

Journal Metadata Exchange Format - an open format to share journal metadata

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Version: 1.0 (Preprint, October 2025)

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Abstract

This article presents the motivation, design and use of the Journal Metadata Exchange Format (JMEF), an open XML-based format for exchanging journal-level metadata. Originating from the needs of the Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH) within the CRAFT-OA and DIAMAS initiatives, JMEF 1.0 provides a clearly defined structure compatible with OAI-PMH, multilingual fields, and support for operational diamond open-access criteria for journals. We describe why existing formats (Dublin Core, JATS, KBART, Crossref) proved insufficient, outline the structure of JMEF with an example XML record, and summarize current implementations (DDH, OJS plugin, Polish Library of Science) together with planned extensions and governance for further development.

Diamond Discovery Hub and Journal Metadata

The need for data exchange in DDH

At the beginning of 2024, work began on the European CRAFT-OA¹ project. More than a year earlier, another project, DIAMAS², had started. The aim of both projects was to strengthen and develop open access to scholarly publications in Europe, with particular emphasis on diamond open access. Each project, however, focused on a different aspect of this goal: DIAMAS emphasized development strategies and recommendations, whereas the core of CRAFT-OA comprised tasks related to operations and technologies supporting diamond open access.

¹ Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access, <https://www.craft-oa.eu>, Horizon Europe project

² Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication, <https://diamasproject.eu>, Horizon Europe project

One of the outcomes of CRAFT-OA was the creation of the Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH), a web platform that contains an index of diamond journals³. The criteria for determining whether journals qualify as "diamond" were developed by a joint task force with contributors from both the CRAFT-OA and DIAMAS projects. Of course, for the newly created DDH system to provide such data, they first had to be present in it. Moreover, it was not enough to enter them just once—they had to be kept up to date. Where can one obtain journal metadata⁴ that are continuously updated and trustworthy? In DDH, we defined the concept of *trusted sources*, i.e. systems that supply DDH with data verified by a reliable institution managing such a system. Being a trusted source presupposes compliance with the Diamond OA criteria and the DDH Terms of Service. Publishers and publishing service providers can become trusted data sources for the Diamond Discovery Hub (DDH). Technically, such a source may be, for example, an OJS⁵ instance or some custom publisher platform. The role of a trusted source may also be fulfilled by other systems such as aggregators, national nodes, and similar entities. This article is not the right place to describe DDH in detail or the process of connecting journal data sources to it. Readers interested in those details will find more information at <https://ddh.diamas.org/docs>.

For the purposes of this article, the most important point is that work on DDH created the need for the automatic harvesting of journal data from source systems. To make this possible, such a system had to collect the relevant data and expose them via an API in a defined way so that DDH could harvest them. This made it necessary to choose a suitable data exchange format.

Searching for the right metadata format

From the very beginning, we were aware that we would not find a journal-metadata exchange format that covers diamond criteria for journals. Such a format could not exist yet because these criteria were only recently defined within the DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA projects. Nevertheless, for reasons of openness and interoperability with other solutions, we considered it best to adopt an existing standard format and extend it with the diamond criteria. Before starting the search, we defined three main expectations for such a format:

- The format must allow for the transfer of the journal metadata we needed: titles, ISSN, eISSN, publisher data, licenses, article languages, etc.
- The format should be strictly definable and allow for hierarchical data structures (e.g., XML or JSON, but not CSV, for which it is hard to define a schema and which is a tabular, two-dimensional format).
- The format should be able to fit within OAI-PMH⁶, which is a standard for exposing resources and is supported by many standard software libraries. OAI-PMH makes it

³ The platform is available at <https://ddh.diamas.org>

⁴ In the context of journals, the terms "metadata," "data," and "information" are used interchangeably in this article

⁵ Open Journal System, <https://pkp.sfu.ca/software/ojs>

⁶ The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting, <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh>

possible, for example, to query data providers for resources that were added within a given time frame. The protocol is a very general envelope for the data inside, which can be defined by any other format that describes the data. The only OAI-PMH requirement for the internal format is that it must be defined (like OAI-PMH itself) as XML. Therefore, we narrowed our choice to XML-based formats.

To our surprise, when analyzing formats known in the open-science world, we did not find a single one that satisfied what seemed to us to be quite basic assumptions. The widely used XML-based Dublin Core format⁷ can describe arbitrary resources, but it turned out to be too generic for our needs (it lacks support for many journal-level metadata). Another open-science XML format, JATS⁸, was primarily designed for the transfer of article data. Journal metadata appear in it essentially as a subset of publication metadata and do not contain all the elements we required (licenses, languages). The KBART format⁹ focuses on exchanging information about journal contents rather than journal metadata as such. It is a CSV format and allows extensions with additional columns. Unfortunately, the CSV structure rules out its use in OAI-PMH and makes it difficult to define hierarchical data structures. It also hinders a strict and precise definition of the structure (due to the lack of a schema). The Crossref format¹⁰ supports XML (and JSON) and offers some journal metadata. Unfortunately, the set of fields is quite limited. It does not allow for adding, for example, keywords, OECD¹¹ classifications, licenses, or languages.

Using one of the above formats and extending it was either impossible in our case or burdened with significant overhead and the difficulty of adhering to their constraints. And of course there remained the lack of support for diamond criteria.

The creation of the open JMEF format

In this situation, we decided to create our own format, free of the above limitations and meeting all our requirements. We also concluded that the format could fill the gap we had identified and might be useful in other systems that require the exchange of journal metadata. For this reason, in designing it we aimed to give it a general and standard character. JMEF is an XML format (defined and described in an XSD schema¹²), and thus can be used as a carrier of information within the OAI-PMH protocol. The names of tags and attributes correspond to specific journal metadata. The current version, 1.0, defines a set of basic journal properties that can be transferred between systems. It is not overly extensive, making it easy to understand and apply, while providing a stable basis for future extensions with new metadata.

⁷ Dublin Core, <https://www.dublincore.org>

⁸ Journal Article Tag Suite, <https://jats.nlm.nih.gov>

⁹ Knowledge Bases And Related Tools, <https://www.niso.org/standards-committees/kbart>

¹⁰ <https://www.crossref.org/documentation/schema-library>

¹¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fields_of_Science_and_Technology

¹² Schema for JMEF 1.0 is available at <https://jmfef.icm.edu.pl/version-1.0/jmfef.xsd>

Description of JMEF 1.0

Below is an example XML in JMEF 1.0 together with a brief description of the individual sections. Detailed documentation of all current versions of the format, along with the schema, is available at <https://journalmetadata.org>.

```
<journal xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink">

  <id type="ddh">123</id>
  <id type="doaj">6f0107092faa43e7b3232480cb89fb99</id>
  <id type="doi">10.1012/abc</id>

  <title-group>
    <title language-iso2="ENG">Patria Artha Technological Journal</title>
    <other-title type="translation" language-iso2="DEU">Translated title</other-title>
    <other-title type="subtitle" language-iso2="ENG">Subtitle</other-title>
    <other-title type="alternative">Alt title</other-title>
  </title-group>

  <issn publication-format="print">1063-777X</issn>
  <issn publication-format="electronic">1090-6517</issn>

  <diamond-criteria>
    <scholarly-journal value="true" />
    <community-owned value="true"/>
    <open-access-with-open-licenses value="true" />
    <no-fees value="true"/>
    <open-to-all-authors value="true" />
  </diamond-criteria>

  <organizations>
    <publisher>
      <name>British Medical Journal</name>
      <location>
        <country iso3="GBR">United Kingdom</country>
      </location>
    </publisher>
    <other-organization>
      <name>University of Science</name>
    </other-organization>
    <other-organization>
      <name>University of Science 2</name>
    </other-organization>
  </organizations>

  <publication-policy>
    <review-process type="peer"/>
    <languages>
      <language iso2="ENG">English</language>
      <language iso2="DEU">German</language>
      <language>Polish</language>
    </languages>
    <licenses>
      <license xlink:href="http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0" />
      <license xlink:href="http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0" />
    </licenses>
  </publication-policy>

</journal>
```

```

<self-uri xlink:href="http://ejournal.patria-artha.ac.id/index.php/patj/index" />

<keywords>
  <keyword>DNA analysis</keyword>
  <keyword>gene expression</keyword>
  <keyword>parallel cloning</keyword>
  <keyword>fluid microarray</keyword>
</keywords>

<classifications>
  <classification type="oecd-2007">
    <class code="2.6" value="Medical engineering" />
  </classification>
</classifications>

</journal>

```

As shown in the example above, the metadata are grouped into sections corresponding to areas of information typical of a journal:

- id – various journal identifiers for internal use by systems exchanging data, e.g., for synchronization or deduplication of harvested data,
- title group – titles associated with the journal. The main journal title is required; other title types are optional,
- issn – ISSN numbers (for print and electronic editions),
- diamond criteria – the journal-diamond criteria defined within the DIAMAS and CRAFT-OA projects [[link](#)],
- organizations – institutions associated with the journal, in particular the publisher.
- publication policy – a set of policies related to the publication process in the journal, e.g., the review process,
- self URI – the URL of the journal's website,
- keywords – any keywords related to the journal,
- classifications – standardized classifications of the journal's subject area.

It is worth noting a few aspects of the JMEF definition:

- It is a format closely tied to journals. Journal metadata are not merely an add-on to other data but the primary entities on which the protocol focuses. Combined with the XML structure, this allows for clear data definitions and a precise schema,
- It can be used within OAI-PMH, but is not dependent on it. The identifiers section makes it possible to synchronize journal data between systems even if JMEF is used without the OAI-PMH envelope,
- It supports multilingualism. It allows one to specify the language of a given information fragment (e.g., a title) and the languages in which the journal publishes,

- It supports the operational diamond OA criteria for journals, for the first time defined and described so precisely.

Current use of JMEF

JMEF was initially created with the aim of enabling DDH to harvest data from other source systems. DDH can connect to any system that exposes an API in the OAI-PMH/JMEF format or in pure JMEF. Moreover, DDH not only harvests data in JMEF but also makes the metadata of the collected journals available using this format¹³. Any system can automatically harvest these data without the need for authorization, as long as it implements JMEF itself.

Beyond DDH, an application using JMEF to share journal metadata is the OJS publishing system — specifically, an OJS JMEF plugin developed by Masaryk University Press (Munipress) within the CRAFT-OA project¹⁴. The plugin allows adding journal diamond criteria to an OJS instance and sharing the journal metadata in the JMEF format.

This is not the only system. Work is currently underway to implement a JMEF-based API in the largest open-science publication system in Poland, i.e., the Polish Library of Science¹⁵. Like DDH, this system is being developed by the ICM University of Warsaw software development team. It will soon expose metadata for more than 1700 journals via OAI-PMH/JMEF and will become one of the trusted data providers for DDH.

Future development of JMEF

So far, conceptual and development work on JMEF has taken place mainly within the CRAFT-OA project for the DDH. In addition, JMEF development has become one of the topics addressed by the Tool & Technology Task Force of the European Diamond Capacity Hub. In the near future, a dedicated task force focused on JMEF development is planned. As for extending the format definition, the first ideas are already emerging. It has not yet been decided when they will be implemented; what is certain is that the format will be maintained and developed. JMEF was created in response to specific needs in CRAFT-OA, but it was designed to enable broadly understood journal-metadata exchange. We believe that wider use of the format could in the future simplify and standardize machine-readable sharing of journal data, as well as enhance the interoperability of systems that store journal information. We will certainly support every adoption of the format and invite the entire publishing community to discuss its further development.

¹³ List of diamond journals in DDH OAI-PMH/JMEF:
https://ddh.diamas.org/oai/journals?verb=ListRecords&metadataPrefix=oai_jmef

¹⁴ <https://github.com/munipress/jmef>

¹⁵ <https://bibliotekanauki.pl>

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank all members of the CRAFT-OA project for their valuable feedback during the development of the JMEF format, and in particular **Radek Gomola**, author of the OJS JMEF plugin, for his constructive comments on the JMEF format. The authors also thank **Hanna Varachkina** for editorial review and constructive suggestions which improved the clarity and substance of the manuscript.